

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Long Fiber Spray-up Molding Optimization of Chopped Glass Fiber Reinforced Polydicyclopentadiene Composites

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Out-of-Autoclave (OOA)

- Composite materials have high stiffness to weight ratio.
- In the application of Autoclave, “work-intensive wet laminating techniques” or prepregs are used.
- However, high manufacturing cost and low rate of production.
- Cost and the rate production is the most key factors in the automotive industries.

Figure 1 Estimated 2013-2022 market for total aerospace composite structures vs OOA

Liquid Composite Molding Technology

- OOA Technologies and also can be semi-automated.
- For both RTM and S-RIM, preforms are laid inside the mold in prior to injection.
- Preform plant, storage, transportation and manual handling still very expensive.
- R-RIM uses fillers or chopped reinforcements.

- Resin Transfer Molding (RTM)

- Reaction Injection Molding (RIM)

Why Long Fiber Injection (LFI)?

- In the application of R-RIM length of reinforcements or fillers are limited to 0.5mm.
- Fully Automated
- High Fiber volume fraction
- Preform plant, storage, transportation and manual handling can be eliminated or significantly be reduced.
- Injected fiber length maximum 50~70mm.
- Maximum of 50% fiber volume fraction possible.

Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD)

- Colorless liquid with a low viscosity
- Activated by catalyst, Ring Opening Metathesis Polymerization (ROMP)
- Molybdenum (Mo), Tungsten (W), Titanium (Ti), Ruthenium (Ru) based Catalysts
- Restrictions related to instability in atmosphere and an expensive catalyst (Ru based)

Lab-scale Apparatus

- Lab-scale apparatus moves and sprays the mixture of resin and the fiber along the horizontal coordinates.
- Two lines of the mixture were sprayed onto the mold surface.
- Once the spray was completed, it was compression molded in a hot-plate in order to cure the part.

2 completed spray result

Mixture spray to the mold surface

Resin trap, spray nozzle & fiber spray gun

Lab-scale Apparatus

Research Objectives

- **Achieving uniform fiber volume distribution over the mold surface**
 - Spray height effect (150mm, 200mm & 250mm)
 - Fiber length effect (fiber lengths, 25mm & 50mm)
 - Fiber weight percentage effect (20wt% & 30wt%)
- **Analysis of fiber entanglement effect during compression molding**
 - Tensile strength examination for different fiber lengths and a binder for the matrix
 - Fiber entanglement modeling
- **Different spray pattern analysis**
 - Examination of different spray patterns to achieve uniform fiber volume distribution
 - Different mold geometries

Uniform fiber volume distribution

- For the fiber length of 25mm, height and the weight percentage had no specific pattern or significance on the uniformity of distribution.
- For the fiber length of 50mm, uniformity of the distribution was dependent on increasing the spray height.

Fiber Entanglement Analysis

- Approximately four to five different fiber lengths are considered to be experimented.
- **Experimental procedure**
 - Individual lengths are impregnated with a very weak matrix and cured.
 - A very weak matrix must be used in order to minimize the load holding effect at the interphase between the fiber and resin
 - Tensile tests of the specimen is undertaken.
 - **Matrix: Emulsion binder**

Fiber Entanglement Analysis

Spray Pattern Analysis

- Different spray patterns were considered in order to achieve uniform mechanical properties throughout the part.
- The MATLAB CODE should be further enhanced in order to clarify the fiber concentrated areas.
- Only the plane mold geometry was considered but in the future, different mold geometries will be encountered.

